

A New Year's Perspective on the Global Hunt for Particle Dark Matter

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Scope of Perspective

- **2025 in review**
 - Xe detectors
 - NaI targets
 - Quantum technologies
- **In anticipation**
 - SuperCDMS
 - NaI targets
 - DarkSide-20k
 - TESSERACT
- **2025 Externalities to Direct Detection**

So far, the Nobel Committee has not returned my calls.

Webcomic from Saturday Morning Breakfast Cereal

A Unified Vision coming from SNOWMASS

A Chou, SNOWMASS Dark Matter Plenary

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2025 Updates

Running experiments continued to make progress: greater sensitivity, greater understanding of detectors.

More science coming out of these detectors than just canonical WIMP searches: now all 3 xenon experiments have seen 8B solar neutrinos from CEVNS.

Spin Independent Direct DM status

arXiv:2203.08084

Focus on spin-independent DM-nuclear scattering

Michael Lucibella 2014, APS.org

Running Xenon Experiments

- Leading WIMP sensitivity
- 3 running experiments that will continue ~5 years
 - XENONnT has had a hardware upgrade for its grids
- Science also with electronic recoils, effective field theory models, MIMPs,

WIMP search 2024 (published in 2025) Phys. Rev. Lett. 135,011802

Neutrinos in Xenon Experiments

- All 3 xenon detectors have seen B8 Solar neutrinos:
 - XENONnT PRL 133 191002 (2024)
 - PandaX-nT PRL 133 191001 92024)
 - LZ arXiv: 2512.08065

- Other neutrinos play a large role in our detectors
 - $0\nu\beta\beta$ searches with ^{136}Xe (2 $\nu\beta\beta$ rate seen in XENONnT)
 - DEC ^{124}Xe : measured half life, detector effects seen

Plenary talk tomorrow, parallel talks yesterday

NaI crystals: DAMA/LIBRA signal

DAMA/NaI+DAMA/LIBRA-phase1+DAMA/LIBRA-phase2 (2.86 ton × yr)

2-6 keV

$$A \cos[\omega(t-t_0)]$$

- Annual Modulation seen at $>13\sigma$
- Not SI isospin-conserving
- Isospin-violating SI at $\sim 10 \text{ GeV}/c^2$,
 - or SD at 10 or 45 GeV/c^2
 - key reason to think about low mass
- Also studied with updated quenching

Nal tests: ongoing

- ANAIS-112, running, COSINE100 ended, but new data taking starting: published a combined result: 4.7 and 3.5 σ rejection of DAMA for 1-6 and 2-6 keV
- COSINE saw that how calibrations are handled can induce a modulation of residuals, Moved lab in 2023.
- COSINUS cryogenic search with discrimination, started this year. Quenching in crystals studied.

ANAIS SciAdv 7 46 '21

COSINE-100 & ANAIS Combined

Is it just an analysis artifact? [arXiv:2208.05158](https://arxiv.org/abs/2208.05158)

[arXiv:2503.19555](https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.19555)

So many new detectors...

so many ~~hot~~ **cold** technologies: SNSPDs, TESs, KIDs, MMCs, superfluid He, superconducting QUBITs ...

Recent Updates

- DAMIC-M prototypes at LSM with 1.3 kg-day : limits on DM- electron
- (New updates from SENSEI running at SNOLab with 1 e- threshold)
- DAMIC-M running this year-> going for kg-yr exposure
- DAMIC-M and OSCURA might be in funding limbo

- TESSERACT with <3 g-hr on surface Si nucleon interactions
 - energy resolution of ~360 meV
- TESSERACT planned for 2028 operations

Low energy excess (LEE)

EXCESS initiative: SciPost Phys. Proc. 9, 001 (2022)

- Not Dark Matter
- Not (all) the same backgrounds
 - Phonons affected by both holder and inter-layer sensor stresses
 - Charge readout affected by radiation induced backgrounds
- DAMIC (SNOLAB) LEE levels not yet probed by new experiments
- General quantum effect? Wider Impact

Anticipating 2026 and further to the future

SuperCDMS will commence data-taking.

Nal answers should come

And in further years: DarkSide-20k and TESSERACT (& NEWS-G, PICO, etc)

SuperCDMS

OI-PLR comparison

	Germanium	Silicon
HV	Lowest threshold for low mass DM Larger exposure, no ³² Si bkgd	Lowest threshold for low mass DM Sensitive to lowest DM masses
iZIP	Nuclear Recoil Discrimination Understand Ge Backgrounds	Nuclear Recoil Discrimination Understand Si Backgrounds

- Under construction at SNOLAB: running this year...
- 4 towers: 1 Ge iZIP, 1 Ge & Si iZIP, 2 Ge & Si HV
- Programme, including new detectors and upgrades discussed at arXiv:2203.08463

Nal tests: future

COSINUS

arXiv:2507.02429

- Multiple Nal detectors - we'd like to know the cause of the modulation, not just rule out DM.

- COSINUS results with 1 year would rule out DAMA
- SABRE: low bkgd crystals, with Northern and Southern sites, also starting this year.
 - SABRE South 3σ exclusion in 2 years • 5σ confirmation in 3 years

SABRE

Seasonal effect

Dark Matter

- NEW opportunity for LNGS
 - DAMA is decommissioned, INFN owns the crystals, they could be used in a future experiment

DarkSide-20k

- DarkSide-20k under construction at LNGS
- Technology advances in SiPMs, Underground Ar

Technologies new and old

- Signals from nuclear recoils
- Semiconductor targets: Si, Ge
- Scintillating bolometers CaWO₄
- Spherical Proportional Counter
- Scintillating Bubble Chamber (LAr)

Unknown impacts on Direct Detection

LSST started data-taking

DESI results indicate $w=-1$ not likely

US funding is not meeting P5 recommendations

Cosmology

Significance of rejection of Λ CDM:

- ▶ DESI+CMB+Pantheon+: 2.8σ
- ▶ DESI+CMB+Union3: 3.8σ
- ▶ DESI+CMB+DESY5: 4.2σ

Elbers Talk Oct 25

We are learning more about Λ CDM from other fields:
most important in the last year:

- DESI results on dynamic dark energy
- and beginning data taking of Vera Rubin Observatory

The Future

But particle astrophysicists
want DETECTORS to find
Dark Matter

US DOE comments in December

- Some dispiriting predictions from XKCD last year
- But worse was news from the US DOE, delivered in the DPF community meeting <https://indico.global/event/15767/>
 - No US DOE support for XLZD for 5+ years

UK+Europe+Others: planning a staged approach to XLZD to begin science prior to US involvement

DPF Community Meeting

Dec 18, 2025, 9:45AM → Dec 19, 2025, 5:30PM America/New_York

Our Current Status

A Chou, SNOWMASS Dark Matter Plenary

If we Search Deep and Wide, in 20 years

A Chou, SNOWMASS Dark Matter Plenary

BLOOM COUNTY

by Berkeley Breathed

Direct detection experiments have continued to probe new parameter space, and these sensitive detectors are capable of searches not thought of a decade ago.

This must all be taken in conjunction with axion/wavelike DM searches, collider searches, and astrophysical evidence.

I hope there is a dark sector with many interesting new particles, which solve current mysteries and open new ones.

More Recent Updates

- SNSPD devices also get to 100s of meV
- clean digital signals with low backgrounds

QROCODILE

arXiv:2412.16279v2

Low Mass Dark Matter Search technologies

CRESST, SuperCDMS, COSINUS, EDELWEISS ^{NEW} Transition-Edge-Sensor (TES)

- Thin-film deposited on crystals
- Strong R-T dependence at superconducting transition
- Sensitive to athermal phonons

- Bubble chambers have a benefit of being insensitive to electron recoils
- the dE/dx is too low to nucleate a bubble
- but need to worry about alphas and neutrons
- additional acoustic or optical channels help

Spin Independent Direct DM status

Liquid Noble TPC technology dominates $> 10 \text{ GeV}$

Michael Lucibella 2014, APS.org